

A new species of the genus *Emiliotia* (Gastropoda, Trochoidea) from deep water of Cuba

Una nueva especie del género *Emiliotia* (Gastropoda, Trochoidea) de aguas profundas de Cuba

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ABSTRACT

A new species of the genus *Emiliotia* Faber, 2006 from deep waters of the North of Cuba is described, comparing it with *Emiliotia rubrostriata* (Rolán, Rubio & Fernández-Garcés, 1997), type species of the genus, and *Emiliotia immaculata* Ortea, Espinosa & Fernández-Garcés, 2008, which are the only two previously known species.

RESUMEN

Se describe una nueva especie del género *Emiliotia* Faber, 2006 de aguas profundas del Norte de Cuba, comparándola con *Emiliotia rubrostriata* (Rolán, Rubio & Fernández-Garcés, 1997) especie tipo del género y con *Emiliotia immaculata* Ortea, Espinosa & Fernández-Garcés, 2008, únicas especies previamente conocidas.

INTRODUCTION

ROLÁN, RUBIO & FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS (1997) described *Botrophoma rubrostriatum* from Cienfuegos Bay, Cuba, and placed it provisionally in the genus *Botrophoma* Thiele, 1921 (Turbinidae: Colloniinae), based on its calcareous operculum and certain morphological characters of its shell.

FABER (2006) erected the genus *Emiliotia* for *Botrophoma rubrostriatum* Rolán, Rubio & Fernandez-Garcés, 1997, and placed it in Trochoidea, family Turbinidae Rafinesque, 1815, after comparing and separating it from similar genera like *Rhodionoliotia* Tomlin & Shackleford, 1915 (type species, by OD: *Cyclostrema roseotincta* E. A. Smith, 1871, West Africa); the deep water genus *Moelleriopsis* Bush, 1897 (type species, by OD *M. abyssicola* Bush, 1897);

Bothropoma isseli Thiele, 1924 the type species of the genus *Bothropoma* Thiele, 1924; and *Leptothyra costata* Pease, 1869 type species of the genus *Collonista* Iredale, 1918 (replacement name for *Leptothyra* Pease, 1870).

Between 10th and 25th of May 2017, an expedition to northern Cuban waters, between La Habana Bay and San Antonio Cap, was organized. This expedition, which used the ship Weatherbird II, resulted from cooperation between the University of South Florida, University of Texas and Eckerd College, the Centro de Investigaciones Marinas of La Habana University, and the Centro de Estudios Ambientales de Cienfuegos of the Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología

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y Medio Ambiente. Part of the material collected during this expedition is currently being studied and some papers have already been published (FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS, RUBIO & ROLÁN 2017, 2018, 2019a and 2019b). In the present work, a new species, tentatively placed in the genus *Emiliotia* Faber, 2006 is described.

Abbreviations

ANC Acuario Nacional, La Habana, Cuba

CEAC Centro de Estudios Ambientales of Cienfuegos

CFG Collection Raúl Fernández Garcés, Cuba

CIM-UH (Centro de Investigaciones Marinas, University of La Habana, Cuba

MHNS Museo de Historia Natural, Santiago de Compostela

MNCN Museo Nacional de Ciencias Naturales, Madrid

USF University of South Florida

SYSTEMATICS

VETIGASTROPODA Salvini-Plawen, 1980
Superfamily TROCHOIDEA Rafinesque, 1815
Family COLLONIIDAE Cossmann, 1817
Genus *Emiliotia* Faber, 2006

Emiliotia Faber, 2006: 14 [Type species by original designation: *Bothropoma rubrostriatum* Rolán, Rubio & Fernandez-Garcés, 1997].

Diagnosis: in FABER (2006): "Shell very small, solid, semi translucent, white, turbiniform; protoconch minute, isostrophic, sculptured with irregular spirally oriented striae; teleoconch rather low-spired, comparatively thick-shelled, sculptured with weak spiral and axial ribs and grooves; umbilicus wide, crenulate. Peristome entire, weakly thickened. Operculum thin, calcified, paucispiral, with a small central peg on the interior side".

Remarks: *Emiliotia* is a genus whose species are mostly reported from Cuba;

with the exception of Faber's statement (FABER 2006) regarding the presence of *E. rubrostriata* in the Bahamas.

In Cuba, the species of the genus *Emiliotia* have an infralittoral to bathyal distribution; *E. rubrostriata* from Cienfuegos was found between 10 and 56 m deep; *E. immaculata* from Guanahacabibes peninsula, 25-33 m (ORTEA, ESPINOSA & FERNÁNDEZ-GARCÉS 2008); and the new species from off Cayo Jutía, North of Cuba, in bathyal depths.

Emiliotia juliocesari n. sp. (Figure 1A-F)

Type material: Holotype (Figs. 1A) in ANC (ANC.06.3.165) from SL 39-750; 3 paratypes from the type locality (Figs. 1B-D) also in ANC; 2 paratypes in MNCN (15.05/200069), from SL41-750 Bahía Honda; 6 paratypes in CFG.

Material examined: 16 s: Cuba: 10 s, Cayo Jutía, SL39-750, 22.483° N, 84.065° W, 1296 m (type material ANC, CFG); 2 s, SL 41-750 Bahía Honda 23.086° N, 83.197° W, 1513 m (paratypes MNCN); 4 s, SL 42-750 23.098° N, 82.984° W, 1455 m.

Type locality: North of Cuba, Cayo Jutía, 22.483° N, 84.065° W, 1296 m.

Etymology: The specific name is after Julio César Fernández Martorell, son of the first author.

Description: Shell minute (<1.5 mm), as wide as high, turbiniform, formed by 3.3 whorls, non carinate and widely

umbilicate; colour white. The protoconch has a little more than ¾ whorl, with 240 µm in diameter, strongly

Figure 1. *Emiliotia juliocesari* n. sp. A: holotype, 1.34 mm in diameter, North of Cuba, Cayo Jutía, 22.483° N, 84.065° W, 1296 m (ANC); B-D: paratypes, 1.17, 1.29, 1.34 mm, all from the type locality (ANC); E-G: protoconch and detail from a paratype; H: microsculpture of the protoconch.

Figura 1. *Emiliotia juliocesari* n. sp. A: holotipo, 1,34 mm de diámetro, norte de Cuba, Cayo Jutía, 22.483° N, 84.065° W, 1296 m (ANC); B-D: paratipos, 1,17, 1,29, 1,34 mm, todos de la localidad tipo (ANC); E-G: protoconcha y detalle de un paratipo; H: microescultura de la protoconcha.

convex, with a fine, sharp granulation of short, small, branching ridges, irregularly distributed. The teleoconch is formed by 2.5 very loosely coiled whorls, connected to the preceding whorl only for a very short space. Periphery rounded. Ornamentation formed by spiral cords, axial ribs and axial threads. The teleoconch surface is totally covered by very fine axial threads of axially aligned micro-granules. The spiral cords are fine; in apertural view 4 spiral cords can be seen on the first whorl and 14 on the last one. The axial ribs are very prosocline and thick in the subsutural area; scarcely marked on the periphery and the base and again thick on the base and inside the umbilicus. In the subsutural zone and umbilical area, when crossing, the spiral cords form a regular reticle of rectangular/quadrangular spaces, with a sharp tubercle at the point of intersection. Umbilicus wide and deep, with a marked reticulation and thin spiral cords inside. Aperture oval, prosocline; parietal area and base of the columella thick and slightly reflected towards the umbilicus; outer lip with smooth and with a sharp edge, not externally thickened nor modified by the spiral cords. The periostracum (partly preserved in some shells) is dark brown.

Dimensions: the holotype is 1.34 mm in diameter and 1.30 in height. (H/D = 0.90).

Animal, radula and operculum unknown.

Habitat: Bathyal species, dredged between 1296 and 1513 m depth. The substrate is a very fine and sticky yellowish mud.

Distribution: Only known from the type locality.

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Remarks: There is some concern regarding the generic placement. Whereas there is no doubt that this species is congeneric with *Emiliotia immaculata* Ortea, Espinosa & Fernández-Garcés, 2008, the relation of these two species with the type species *Emiliotia rubrostriata* (Rolán, Rubio & Fernández-Garcés, 1997) is not straightforward. The latter is documented to have a calcareous operculum and is almost certainly a collonid. On the other hand, there are no data on the soft parts and operculum of *Emiliotia immaculata* but it has a very prosocline aperture with a fragile edge, not likely to have been holding the round, calcareous operculum of a collonid. For this reason it could be a skeneid, but we considered it is not appropriate to erect a new genus without data on the living animals or with more material. Therefore, the new species is given the same generic placement as *E. immaculata*.

Emiliotia juliocesari n. sp. is characterized by having the protoconch ornamentation formed by short and small branching ridges, differing thereby from the other two known species. It is also diagnosed by the axial threads which completely cover the surface of the teleoconch, attenuated on the convex part, and by the regular reticle on the subsutural and umbilical zones.

It differs from *E. rubrostriata*, by the lack of colour pattern and spiral cords, and the different sculpture of the protoconch.

From *E. immaculata*, it is distinguished for by its thicker axial sculpture; by the reticulate sculpture on its subsutural and umbilical zones; and also by the different ornamentation of the protoconch.

lecting of sediments. Inés Pazos of the Centro de Apoyo Científico y Tecnológico a la Investigación (CACTI) of the University of Vigo made the SEM micrographs. António A. Monteiro, of Lisboa (Portugal) made correction to the language.

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